
Review and Comparison of Nakuru, Kitui and Narok County Energy Plans

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Executive Summary

The Constitution of Kenya 2010 and the Energy Act 2019 require Kenyan Counties to produce independent county energy plans (CEPs). Few have been produced to date; those that have been produced have been undertaken using different methods, all attempting to align with the requirements of CEPs outlined in the Integrated National Energy Planning (INEP) framework. There is no consensus as to which method is most suited to INEP requirements, and INEP itself is still undergoing revision and debate.

In light of this, this working paper compares the CEPs for Nakuru, Kitui and Narok counties against the requirements of the INEP framework. The comparison is based on whether the contents of the CEP contains the information prescribed in the current INEP draft.

The aims of this working paper are twofold. First, we aim to understand the suitability of different CEP production methods given the requirements outlined by INEP. Second, we aim to identify INEP requirements which are not included in existing CEPs, in order to interrogate whether these have been deprioritized or are impossible to meet at county level. This work is intended to be useful to energy sector stakeholders who are producing CEPs and feeding into the INEP revision process.

For each chapter (i.e., topic) which the INEP requires CEPs to contain, the main requirements were systematically listed. Each CEP was searched for evidence that the requirement was met (i.e., a discussion of the topic is provided). Note that no assessment of the quality of the approach used to meet the requirement was undertaken; rather, it is simply evaluated whether the required topic is covered. Where the CEP fully contained a particular requirement, a score of 100% was given for that requirement; where the CEP partially contained the expected information, a score of 50% was given; and where the information wasn't available at all, a score of 0% was given. The scores for each requirement were aggregated across each chapter to obtain a completeness score.

Table 1: Summary of CEP completeness when compared to INEP requirements.

Chapter	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
1. Introduction	71%	100%	100%
2. Resource Assessment	80%	80%	100%
3. Energy Access	69%	75%	100%
4. Energy Efficiency	20%	80%	90%
5. Bio-Energy	15%	15%	90%
6. Electricity	50%	86%	86%
7. Programs & Projects	75%	100%	75%
8. Implementation & Monitoring	100%	33%	100%

A summary of how the CEPs match the INEP requirements for each chapter is shown in Table 1. Scores of above 65% are marked with the colour **green**; scores between 50% and 65% are marked in **amber**; and scores below 50% are marked in **red**. The Narok CEP met over 65% of INEP requirements across all eight chapters. The Kitui CEP met over 65% of INEP requirements in six chapters, but less than 50% of requirements in two chapters

(bio-energy and implementation & monitoring). The Nakuru CEP met over 65% of INEP requirements in five chapters, 50 of requirements in the electricity chapter, and less than 50% of requirements in both the energy efficiency and bio-energy chapters.

A lower engagement was noted across CEPs with the energy efficiency and bio-energy chapters. The inadequate attention to the chapters could be attributed to insufficient sector data. According to unpublished research of CEP data gaps by Loughborough University, none of the datasets required for these two chapters is comprehensively available and publicly accessible.

The detailed results presented in this working paper are intended to show the relative strengths and weaknesses of each of the CEP methods used to produce the three reports. These notably include:

Strengths: The Narok CEP is the only CEP that has done a section on waste-to-energy potential and a chapter on bio-energy; the other CEPs could borrow from these sections. The Kitui county CEP has given comprehensive solutions by addressing energy gaps and other enabling factors to ensure that the projects are successful and sustainable. The Nakuru CEP has best accounted for budgeting by giving a comprehensive breakdown of the annual budget for different activities; it has also laid out a robust monitoring and evaluation framework with targets given to allow for day-to-day, quarterly, annual, mid-term, and end-of-term monitoring.

Weaknesses: The Kitui CEP may be improved by adopting the structure suggested by the INEP framework to make it easily digestible and comparable to the other CEPs. It should also be augmented by adding the missing chapter on bio-energy and more details on implementation and monitoring. The Nakuru CEP should add the energy efficiency and bio-energy chapters and add modelling of electricity supply in order to meet INEP requirements. The Narok CEP can be improved by addition of a comprehensive explanation of how the modelling scenarios for electricity demand were selected; examples of development partners who could help in the implementation of various projects could also be added.

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Acronyms

CAFOD	Catholic Agency for Overseas Development
CAPI	Computer-Aided Personal Interviews
CEP	County Energy Plan
CIDP	County Integrated Development Plan
EAE	Energy Access Explorer
EDM	Energy Delivery Models
GIZ	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit
IIED	International Institute for Environment and Development
INEP	Integrated National Energy Plan
LCE	Least Cost Electrification
LPG	Liquified Petroleum Gas
MoE	Ministry of Energy
MSE	Micro and Small-scale Enterprise
OnSSSET	Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
UK PACT	UK Partnering for Accelerated Climate Transitions
WRI	World Resources Institute

1 Introduction

This working paper compares county energy plans produced in Nakuru, Kitui, and Narok against the requirements of Kenya's Integrated National Energy Planning framework.

The decentralization of responsibility for energy planning to county level began with the Constitution of Kenya 2010 [1], which divided Kenya into 47 new counties. Each county gained decentralized administrative responsibilities, including energy planning. The Kenya Energy Act 2019 [2] institutionalized this responsibility more specifically by requiring each county government to develop or revise and submit a county energy plan (CEP) to the energy cabinet secretary every three years.

Each CEP is intended to outline the county's energy requirements and goals. The CEPs are to be consolidated with plans from the national energy service providers (e.g., Kenya Power, the Ministry of Energy) to develop the country's Integrated National Energy Plan (INEP). A draft framework for INEP has been produced, but has not yet been enacted. To guide counties in developing the CEPs, the Ministry of Energy has outlined the CEP development process and CEP structure in Chapters 3 and 5 of this INEP framework respectively. The other chapters in the framework relevant to CEPs include Chapter 4 on mainstreaming cross-cutting issues in energy plans, Chapter 8 on institutional and coordination framework for INEP implementation, and Chapter 9 on data management.

Of Kenya's 47 counties, six are known by the authors to have a complete CEP, 15 have ongoing efforts to produce CEPs, and the remaining 26 have made no official progress towards producing a CEP [3]. Of the six CEPs that have been developed so far, three were available to the research team upon request (i.e., Nakuru, Kitui and Narok CEPs). As such, these counties form the basis of this study. Different agencies developed these CEPs following slightly different methodologies. This report reviews their development methods and contents, as guided by the INEP framework.

2 CEP Development Methodologies

Each of the three counties being studied – Nakuru, Kitui, and Narok – used a different methodology to produce their CEP. This section summarizes each county's approach.

2.1 Nakuru Methodology

The Nakuru CEP was authored by a team of consultants from EED Advisory supported by the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) under the framework of the Covenant of Mayors in Sub-Saharan Africa initiative. It was financially supported by the European Union and the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development. It was published in April 2022 and is available online [4].

The process of CEP development was as follows:

1. First, an in-depth review of national and sub-national policies, laws and plans, census data, county-level databases, and geospatial resources, among others, was undertaken.
2. Primary data collection was carried out at the household, institution, and business levels to understand the status of energy access, consumption, and efficiency measures undertaken by learning institutions, health facilities, and businesses. Four hundred and twenty (420) households, 197 health facilities, 128 learning institutions and 384 commercial enterprises across the eleven sub-counties were surveyed. Computer-

Aided Personal Interview¹ (CAPI) tools were employed for these surveys, specifically the SurveyCTO application [6]. Additionally, 11 key informants were interviewed from government agencies, the private sector, non-governmental organisations, and other development partners.

3. The Low Emissions Analysis Platform (LEAP) [7] was used for energy demand modelling covering three scenarios: the business as usual scenario, SDG7 scenario and the high economic growth scenario. The demand modelling was done for electricity demand (including the domestic, commercial, and industrial sectors) and cooking fuel demand (that is demand for, wood, charcoal, LPG, biogas and kerosene).

2.2 Kitui Methodology

The Kitui CEP was developed in collaboration between Kitui's Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources (MENR), CARITAS Kitui, the Catholic Agency for Overseas Development (CAFOD), and the International Institute for Environment and Development (IIED).

This CEP was developed using the Energy Delivery Models (EDM) [8] approach developed by CAFOD and IIED. This method looks at both energy solutions and socio-cultural and contextual factors that significantly impact the acceptance and sustained uptake of energy solutions. The project for producing the CEP ended in July 2022 [9], and a final CEP report has been made available to the authors, though it is not available online to the authors' knowledge at time of writing.

The process of CEP development was as follows:

1. A baseline survey was conducted in 96 households, and interviews were undertaken with an undisclosed amount of county administrators. These activities aimed to collect primary demographic and socioeconomic data, information on road infrastructure, levels of access to electricity and cooking technologies, access to community services (health and education), and information on priority development needs at the level of households, communities and livelihoods.
2. This was followed by a series of in-depth participatory need assessment workshops at the ward level. In total, eight workshops were carried out (i.e., a workshop was held in one ward of each of Kitui's eight sub-counties). Workshop representatives were selected to represent the county's geographic and socioeconomic distribution and cultural mix, and to include vulnerable and marginalised groups.
3. From these workshops, priority needs were identified and ranked. The top three priority needs were found to be: improved farmer income from rain-fed crops; access to clean water in closer proximity for drinking and washing; and better access to health services in remote areas.
4. Once the priority needs were identified, further research was undertaken to understand gaps, barriers and opportunities, including enabling policies, specific socio-cultural obstacles, and enabling factors. The exact research methodology is not defined. This was then followed by solutions development to address the gaps and meet the priority needs.
5. The Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool [10] (OnSSET) was used to model the demand and supply of electricity to households.

2.3 Narok Methodology

The County Government of Narok developed the CEP through a consortium which included technical officers from County Government and experts from Strathmore University En-

¹CAPI is defined as a "face-to-face data collection method in which the interviewer uses a tablet, mobile phone or a computer to record answers given during the interview" [5].

ergy Research Centre (SERC) and World Resources Institute (WRI). Funding was provided through UK Partnering for Accelerated Climate Transitions (UK PACT), a programme funded by the UK Government. It was intended to launch in December 2022, following a final validation workshop [11] – however, the final CEP is still not made publicly available online.

The process of CEP development was as follows:

1. Stakeholder mapping and engagement were conducted to understand policy developments, current projects, and to obtain required data. Governmental stakeholders included the Ministry of Energy, Kenya Power, the Energy and Petroleum Regulation Authority (EPRA), the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation (REREC), the Off-Grid Solar Access Project (KOSAP), and the National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS). Other stakeholders included civil society organisations and the community, engaged through surveys and focus group discussions considering different subsets (e.g., households, SMEs, institutions; split by gender, age, etc).
2. In consultation with relevant stakeholders, a data wish-list for CEP development was compiled. Following the data needs identified in the data wish-list, secondary data collection from global, national and sub-national reports and databases available in the public domain was undertaken.
3. Secondary data was verified through quantitative surveys. The sample size was 665 households, 58 educational institutions, 27 healthcare facilities, 790 micro and small-scale enterprises (SMEs) and three cottage industries. Surveys were conducted using the KoBo collection application installed on Android devices.
4. Possible scenarios for the county's future energy supply and demand were modelled using OnSSET. Clean cooking modelling was undertaken using LEAP, which considered firewood, charcoal, biogas and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) as fuel options for cooking.
5. A customised version of the Energy Access Explorer [12] was developed for the county. This open-source dynamic geospatial information system enables stakeholders to visualise and analyse high-priority areas where access to energy should be expanded.

2.4 Summary

The methodologies used to develop the three CEPs are quite different. Table 2 highlights the differences in terms of survey sample sizes, survey tools used, modelling tools used, and scenarios modelled.

The Narok county CEP approach conducted the most household surveys (665), while the Nakuru approach conducted about two-thirds of that count (420) and the Kitui approach only conducted about one seventh of that count (96). This is a notable difference, and is despite Narok County having the fewest households according to the 2019 census. According to the census, the number of households in Narok, Nakuru, and Kitui as of 2019 was 241,125, 616,046, and 262,942 respectively [13] - as such, the Narok sample size was 0.28%, the Nakuru sample size was 0.07%, and the Kitui sample size was 0.04% of their respective numbers of households. We see no proportionality between the households surveyed and the population of the county. For future county energy planning efforts, it will therefore be important to agree on what is a sufficient sample size for primary data collection to ensure consistency.

In terms of surveying educational facilities, health facilities, SMEs and industries we see variance in how this was undertaken among the counties. There is no indication that in Kitui county there was a survey for these facilities, save for asking the households if they had access to the facilities. In Narok and Nakuru, where the facilities were surveyed, it is not clear what sampling criteria was used to arrive at the number of facilities to be surveyed (i.e., 120 educational institutions, 197 health facilities, and 384 SMEs in Nakuru; 58 educational

Table 2: Summary of the Methodologies Used

	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
Households Surveyed	420	96	665
Education Institutions Surveyed	120	N/A	58
Health Facilities Surveyed	197	N/A	27
SMEs Surveyed	384	N/A	790
Industries Surveyed	N/A	N/A	3
Survey Tool Used	SurveyCTO	N/A	Kobo
Survey Data Collected	Energy Access, Efficiency Measures, Fuel Consumption	Electricity access, grid reliability, cooking methods and fuels, community facilities access, water sources, priority needs, road infrastructure	N/A
Modelling Tools	LEAP	OnSSET	OnSSET, LEAP
What was modelled	Electricity Demand, Cooking Demand	Electrification of Households	Electrification of Households, Electrification of Institutions
Scenarios Modelled	Business as Usual, SDG 7, High Economic Growth	Different Electrification Tiers	Different Electrification Tiers, Forced Grid Electrification
GESI Considered?	N/A	Yes	Yes

institutions, 27 health facilities, and 790 SMEs in Narok). Again, this is another point where symmetry across approaches is critical to ensure fair representation and quality data.

The Nakuru CEP is the only of the three which includes a copy of the survey questions used in data collection in its appendices. As such, it is hard to compare precisely what information was collected across the three efforts. This is obviously problematic – if planners are operating from different baseline data, plans are likely to have inconsistencies. This shows the need to harmonise the requirements for primary data collection exercises, perhaps through a standard survey tool (i.e., questionnaire).

We observe a difference in the modelling tools used across the three counties. To model cooking demand, both Nakuru and Narok CEPs used LEAP for modelling. To model electrification, both Kitui and Narok used OnSSET. Kitui CEP didn't model cooking demand while the Nakuru CEP didn't model electrification. This venn diagram of modelling coverage, again, does not lend itself well to direct comparison. The scenarios modelled also vary across CEPs. Nakuru modelled a business-as-usual, SDG 7, and high economic growth scenario, while Kitui and Narok each modelled scenarios based on different electrification tiers, and Narok additionally added a scenario forcing grid electrification for households with 2km of a transformer. These scenarios cannot all be compared directly. To address this, a common set of energy planning scenarios could be useful. These could be borrowed from any scenarios used in national-level planning and present, and tailored to match the context of each county.

3 CEP Contents

This section compares the contents of the Nakuru, Kitui, and Narok CEPs to the INEP framework requirements across all chapters (i.e., Introduction, Resource Assessment, Energy Access, Energy Efficiency, Bio-Energy, Electricity, Programs and Projects, and Implementation and Monitoring).

Each INEP chapter has multiple requirements. For each requirement in each chapter, it was recorded whether the requirement was completely, partially, or not at all met. Numeric scores were assigned as follows: a score of 1 (or 100%) was assigned where the requirement was met, a score of 0.5 (or 50%) was assigned where it was partially met, and a score

of 0 was assigned where it was not met. These scores were summed over each chapter and divided by the total number of requirements in the chapter to calculate a percentage describing how the CEP meets the INEP requirements for each chapter. The results for each chapter are further described next.

3.1 Introduction

As per the INEP framework, this chapter should provide the background of county energy planning, the process of development of the CEP, the process of integrating the CEP into the County Integrated Development Plan (CIDP), county overview, county energy development partners, and relevant policies and regulatory frameworks for the energy sector. The full list of the main requirements for the chapter, and how the three CEPs satisfied these requirements, is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: INEP Chapter 1 Requirements

	INEP Requirement	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
1	Background & rationale of county energy planning	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Process of the CEP development	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	Process of integrating the CEP into CIDP	No	Yes	Yes
4	County Overview (Location, demographics and economy)	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	Development partners in the county energy sector	No	Yes	Yes
6	Policy and regulatory framework for energy sector	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	Applicable legislations on energy in the county	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Score	71%	100%	100%

Nakuru CEP: The introduction gives the rationale behind the development of the CEP. It provides an overview of the county regarding geographical location, sub-counties, demographics and climatological zones. It also gives an overview of the county's electricity sector, including the major initiatives by national energy suppliers. In addition, the Chapter provides an overview of the methodology used in developing the CEP. However, the introduction neither discusses how the CEP will be integrated into the CIDP nor highlights the development partners in the county energy sector.

Kitui CEP: The introduction discusses the national energy access targets per Kenya's commitment to SDG7. It introduces the Multi-Tier Framework [14] for measuring levels of energy access. It also discusses the energy access initiatives currently being undertaken by the government of Kenya. Finally, it discusses the current policies and regulations on energy access. The methodology for developing the CEP is discussed in Chapter 5, titled "The Process for County Energy Planning". The county topography, climate and socio-economic characteristics are discussed in Chapter 2, titled "The Development Context of Kitui County".

Narok CEP: The introduction gives the rationale for the CEP development. It discusses the history of energy planning in the county. It also highlights the challenges with energy provision in the county. It discusses the methodology employed in developing the CEP. In addition, the CEP gives a list of key stakeholders involved in energy access projects in the county.

Summary: Narok CEP has all the ingredients prescribed by the INEP framework included in the introduction. The Nakuru CEP gives a comprehensive introduction except for the failure to outline the process of integrating the CEP into the CIDP and to list the key energy stakeholders. Although the Kitui CEP has all the ingredients prescribed for the introduction, these are spread across various chapters of the CEP. The Kitui CEP introduction can be improved by rearranging its sections in the order recommended by the INEP framework.

3.2 County Energy Resources Assessment

This section should detail all county energy resources and provide statistical data regarding technical viability and level of current exploitation. Moreover, it should specify the functions of the county government concerning the exploitation of the resources. It should also relate the county's energy resources to national statistics. Further, it should describe energy resources and potential in the county, including projections based on the available data. The resource assessment activity framework should focus on five key dimensions: availability and economic potential, adequacy, sustainability, ease of access and cost of use. The main expected sections for this Chapter are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: INEP Chapter 2 Requirements

	INEP Requirement	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
1	Assessment of biomass energy resources	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Assessment of waste resources	No*	No*	Yes
3	Assessment of geothermal resources	Yes	No	Yes
4	Assessment of hydropower resources	No	No	Yes
5	Assessment of solar resources	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	Assessment of wind resources	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	Assessment of fossil fuels	No	Yes (Coal)	No
8	Assessment of nuclear programs	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Score	80%	80%	100%

*This assessment was expected.

Nakuru CEP: The Nakuru county CEP assesses solar, geothermal, wind, and bioenergy. Geospatial maps are provided for solar, wind, and geothermal resources. The bioenergy section gives the county fuelwood, charcoal, and crop residue demand. In addition, the county net balance for fuel wood is given as well as some of the companies working to produce briquettes in the county. The CEP does not discuss waste-to-energy potential.

Kitui CEP: The Kitui county CEP discusses energy resources in Chapter 3, "Energy Context in Kitui County". Four technologies are discussed: solar, wind, biomass and coal. For wind and solar energy, the potential in the county is given, including capacity factors. The county demand and supply for charcoal and firewood are presented to constitute biomass energy. In addition, emerging issues such as deforestation in the county are discussed. For coal, the size of deposits in the county and the progress and challenges in exploiting the coal reserves are discussed. This CEP does not discuss waste-to-energy potential in the county.

Narok CEP: The CEP discusses five energy technologies: geothermal, hydropower, solar, wind and biomass. Maps of wind and solar potential are provided. For hydropower, the potential sites for small and mini hydropower stations are given. For geothermal, the planned plants in the county are discussed. The biomass energy section for the county is comprehensive - It discusses the potential annual sustainable supply of woodfuel from each sub-county. The section also assesses the potential for biogas production from municipal sewer waste, municipal solid waste, slaughterhouses, livestock and crop residues.

Summary: The energy resources discussed in the three CEPs vary depending on the technologies prevalent in the counties. Only the Narok CEP has assessed the county's waste-to-energy potential in the form of using waste to produce biogas. According to the INEP framework, the two main resource assessment tasks the counties should undertake is that of assessing waste-to-energy potential and assessing biomass energy resources. The rest of the resource potentials should be availed to the counties by the MoE; the counties may then propose plans and actions to complement and enhance national plans and actions in assessing these resources. All the CEPs can be improved by providing a comment on all the resources required to be evaluated; for example, it needs to be clarified whether Kitui and Nakuru do not have hydropower resources or if it is that these were not looked into.

3.3 Energy Access

This chapter should provide an overview of energy access in the county. It should cover the energy access trends, key stakeholders, strategies, goals and barriers to energy access over time. The main INEP requirements for this chapter are given in Table 5.

Table 5: INEP Chapter 3 Requirements

	INEP Requirement	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
1	Policies and regulations for energy access	Yes**	Yes	Yes
2	Key stakeholders in energy access sector	No	No	Yes
3	Past and current energy access initiatives	No	Yes	Yes
4	Access for lighting and for cooking (heating)	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	Energy access trends for households	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	Energy access trends for community services	Yes	No*	Yes
7	Energy access trends for productive use (e.g., MSEs)	Yes	No*	Yes
8	Development of strategies to promote energy access	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Score	69%	75%	100%

*However, solutions are given.

**Not elaborate.

Nakuru CEP: An overview of energy access in households, educational facilities, health facilities and enterprises is provided based on surveys administered through CAPI. Energy access in households, educational facilities, health facilities, and enterprises is discussed in terms of electricity access and heat (thermal) energy, including energy for cooking. The thermal and cooking energy sources assessed are LPG, electricity, firewood, charcoal, ethanol and kerosene. Access is evaluated at the county level except for the electrification of health centres which has been broken down at the sub-county level.

Kitui CEP: For Kitui, energy access is discussed in Chapter 3, "Energy Context in Kitui County". Access is mainly assessed at the household level and split into energy for lighting and cooking. For lighting, the technologies considered are biogas, diesel, petrol, battery, candle, torch, solar, wood, gas lamp, paraffin tin lamp, paraffin lantern, paraffin pressure lamp, and mains electricity. For cooking, the technologies considered are solar, charcoal, firewood, biogas, LPG, paraffin and electricity. The percentage use of each of the technologies is given at each of the sub-counties.

Narok CEP: Energy access is discussed for households, health centres, educational institutions, and infrastructure services, e.g. agriculture and enterprises. Access to lighting and cooking (heating) is assessed for all categories. For lighting, the technologies assessed are solar home systems, grid power, solar lanterns, mini-grids, rechargeable batteries, dry cells and generators. For cooking and heating, the technologies whose usage is assessed are firewood, charcoal, solar, electricity, paraffin, LPG and biogas. Cooking appliances used and their frequency is also evaluated. Flagship projects that will require electrification in the county are also listed. The assessments are broken down at the sub-county level.

Summary: The Narok CEP has all the recommended components for this chapter. The Nakuru CEP has most of the components for this chapter except for its failure to outline the policies, key stakeholders and past and current projects in the county's energy access space. The Kitui CEP has a majority of the expected components for this chapter with an exception of the energy access trends for community services and MSEs; however, the CEP goes ahead to design energy access solutions for all sectors including for community access and MSEs. In terms of the granularity of the analysis, Narok and Kitui county CEPs have their energy access analysis at the sub-county level while the Nakuru county CEP has majority of its analysis at the county level.

3.4 County Energy Efficiency and Conservation Measures Assessment

This chapter should focus on energy efficiency and conservation measures in the county. It should identify the energy efficiency gaps, potential solutions, costs and benefits of the solutions, as well as the potential barriers and constraints in the implementation of the solutions. The energy efficiency discussions should cover 1) households (including usage and efficiency of improved cookstoves, LPG, biogas and lighting bulbs), 2) commercial and institutional buildings (including electricity usage, the efficiency of equipment used and building designs), 3) industries (including energy use by type of industry and number of audited industries and 4) the transport sector (including the number of vehicles transiting the county, number of vehicles used within the county, proportion of people using non-motorised transport, and the number of motorbikes registered in the county). The main expected components of this chapter are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: INEP Chapter 4 Requirements

	INEP Requirement	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
1	Energy efficiency in households	No*	Yes	Yes
2	Energy efficiency in commercial and institutional buildings	No*	Yes	Yes
3	Energy efficiency in industries	No	Yes	Yes
4	Energy efficiency in the transport sector	No	No	Yes**
5	Discussion of gaps, potential solutions, potential impact, potential barriers to implementation	No	Yes	Yes
	Score	20%	80%	90%

*However, considered in solutions.

**Not detailed.

Nakuru CEP: The Nakuru CEP lacks a chapter on energy efficiency in the county. However, energy efficiency has been briefly incorporated in some of the solutions recommended by the CEP. Data on energy efficiency was also collected in their survey process, as evident in the questionnaire attached to the CEP.

Kitui CEP: The CEP gives the barriers and constraints that might hinder energy efficiency interventions in the county. It discusses energy efficiency gaps for households, public institutions, and industrial and business sectors. Finally, it recommends the priority actions to improve energy efficiency in the county. It however fails to discuss the energy efficiency in the transport sector.

Narok CEP: The CEP discusses energy efficiency in buildings, industry and commercial activities, households and institutions. For office buildings, the aspects assessed are building orientation; lighting points; cooling and refrigeration systems; water heating and energy use index. For households, institutions and MSMEs, the assessment was for lighting and cooking equipment. The CEP indicates that the energy efficiency in transport was not undertaken due to data scarcity.

Summary: The Kitui and Narok CEP have a chapter dedicated to energy efficiency and have covered all the expected components except the energy efficiency in the transport sector where the data is scanty. However, only Narok county collected primary data on efficiency, the arguments on efficiency by the Kitui CEP are either general or based on findings of other researches. The Nakuru CEP does not contain an explicit assessment of the energy efficiency in the county.

3.5 Bio-Energy

This chapter should provide an overview of bio-energy initiatives, the challenges, key stakeholders, future bio-energy outlook, and proposed interventions. The components of the chapter include 1) baseline supply of bio-energy (including bio-energy crops, agricultural residues, waste and forest products), 2) bio-energy supply cost, 3) bio-energy, 4) current bio-energy demand situation (in power generation, building sector, manufacturing sector, transport sector, households and institutions) and 5) challenges affecting the bio-energy sector. These full list of expected components for this chapter is shown in Table 7.

Table 7: INEP Chapter 5 Requirements

	INEP Requirement	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
1	Agencies responsible for specific aspects of biomass energy	No	No	No
2	Relevant laws and regulations	No	No	Yes
3	Baseline supply of bio-energy	Yes*	Yes*	Yes
4	Bio-energy supply costs	No	No	Yes
5	Bio-energy trade	No	No	Yes
6	Current bio-energy market and demand situation	Yes*	Yes*	Yes
7	Challenges affecting bio-energy sector	No	Yes*	Yes
8	Cross-cutting issues in bio-energy	No	No	Yes
9	Development of bio-energy goals and strategies	Yes*	No	Yes
10	Future bio-energy costs	No	No	Yes
	Score	15%	15%	90%

*Only for biomass.

Nakuru and Kitui CEPs: These CEPs do not have chapters/sections dedicated to bio-energy other than the chapter/section on biomass resource potential. In Chapter 4, titled "Modelling Energy Demand and Growth", Nakuru CEP has modelled biomass and LPG demand growth scenarios.

Narok CEP: The Narok CEP bioenergy chapter discusses the laws and policies governing the production and consumption of bioenergy; the costs of different bioenergy fuel types (featuring firewood, charcoal, briquettes, bagasse and bioethanol); bioenergy supply chains in the county; and challenges affecting the development of modern bioenergy in the county.

Summary: The Narok County CEP has covered all the expected sections of this chapter. The Nakuru and Kitui CEPs require a Chapter dedicated to assessing and discussing bio-energy in the county beyond the assessments they have done for biomass resources to meet INEP requirements. The low engagement with the bio-energy chapter could be due to the unavailability of data on bioenergy. According to research on CEP data gaps by Loughborough University, none of the seven critical datasets required for the bio-energy chapters is fully available and publicly accessible.

3.6 Electricity

This chapter should include all the issues in the electricity sub-sector, including current and future demand and supply, key stakeholders, key challenges, and proposed interventions. The main expected discussion points of the chapter are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: INEP Chapter 6 Requirements

	INEP Requirement	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
1	List of Key stakeholders in electricity	Yes*	Yes (Inferred)	Yes**
2	Baseline supply and demand	Only demand	Yes	Yes
3	Demand categorised in sector of economy	No	No	No
4	Existing & planned projects	Yes*	Yes**	Yes
5	Cross cutting issues in electricity sector	No	Yes	No (but covered elsewhere)
6	Development of electricity goals and strategies	Only demand scenarios	Yes	Yes
7	Prioritisation of interventions	No	Yes	Yes
	Score	50%	86%	86%

*In introduction chapter.

**In annex.

Nakuru CEP: Electricity demand modelling is done using LEAP. Three demand scenarios are modelled, that is, the business as usual (BAU) scenario, which assumes that the change across the factors that influence energy demand and growth will remain the same; the UN SDG7 Scenario, which assumes that universal access to electricity and clean cooking will be achieved by 2030; and the “High Economic Growth” scenario assumes that the county will experience above-average economic growth, superseding the past, current and generally expected rates. Although this CEP discusses electricity demand comprehensively, it does not assess the electricity supply options to match the demand.

Kitui CEP: Household electrification is modelled using OnSSET, which gives the least cost electrification (LCE) pathway between grid extension and off-grid solutions. The model assumes that urban areas will be connected to tier 4 electricity. For rural areas, scenarios are run for connecting with tier 1, tier 2 and tier 3 electricity. Geospatial maps of the LCE technology are given for each scenario and the investment costs required. Alongside the electrification of households, the electrification of water supply, health centres, agriculture, livestock production, MSEs and the cooking sector is also discussed. The solutions presented are categorised to energy and non-energy solutions.

Narok CEP: Electrification pathways for the county are modelled using OnSSET. The modelling factored in the electrification of households as well as institutions. Three scenarios are considered: (1) connecting urban areas to tier 4 and rural areas to tier 2; (2) connecting urban areas to tier 5 and rural areas to tier 2; and (3) forced grid electrification in which all areas within 2km of the grid are connected to electricity. The results are disaggregated at the county level, and the investments required for each of the sub-counties are given.

Summary: The Narok and Kitui county CEPs have modelled both electricity demand and supply in the counties. Nakuru CEP only modelled electricity demand but not the least cost technologies to supply the required energy. Regarding the OnSSET models, the models for Kitui CEP only include the electrification of households, while that for the Narok CEP included both households and institutions. For Narok and Kitui county CEPs, it is not clear how the scenarios of LCE (i.e., tier targets) were arrived at. The differences in what is modelled and scenarios modelled makes the results different and incomparable for consolidation. It will be important going forward to come up with the guidelines on tools to use and the scenarios to be modelled.

3.7 Programs and Projects

This chapter should include all the agreed interventions to issues identified in the previous chapters. The interventions should consist of those to be undertaken by the national government, county government, non-governmental sector and those planned by development partners. The main components of this chapter are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: INEP Chapter 7 Requirements

	INEP Requirement	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
1	National government projects	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	County government projects	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	Non-governmental and private sector projects	Yes*	Yes	Yes*
4	Development partners	Yes*	Yes	Yes*
	Score	75%	100%	75%

*No examples given.

Nakuru CEP: The CEP discussed the programs that can be undertaken to achieve energy access objectives for four main components: cooking and heating, electricity, sustainable transport, and cross-cutting issues (e.g. energy efficiency and gender equality). The suggested programs contain desired outputs, activities to be undertaken, progress indicators, and the entity responsible. In total, 12 different programs have been proposed. The county government leads on most of the projects with some allocated to the national government, private sector and development partners. However, there are no examples given for these potential developments' partners.

Kitui CEP: Chapter 7, titled "Recommended Priority Investments", presents programs and projects for this CEP. An indicative list of priority investments for Kitui County is given based on the solutions proposed for the county energy sector. The solutions are grouped into seven priority areas for the county: household lighting, water, health, agriculture, livestock, MSEs, and cooking. Each sectoral solution has its specific rationale and criteria for prioritisation. In most cases, further information and analysis are required before finalising the priority investments list and developing an implementation plan. Criteria to assist in the prioritisation are given. An approximate budget for the next steps is also presented based on the cost of components for each of the solutions. The CEP allocates the implementation roles of the projects to the county government, national government and mentioned development partners and private sector players.

Narok CEP: The CEP presents the projects and programs recommended to enhance sustainable modern energy access and energy efficiency and conservation in the county. These projects are categorised into the clean cooking, electricity, and energy efficiency sectors. The proposed project details include timelines, specific activities, implementing agency and project cost. The implementing partners assigned by the CEP are the county government, national government agencies, development partners and the private sector - however, where there are no examples given for the potential development partners or private sector.

Summary: All the CEPs have done well in noting the projects to be undertaken. Whereas the Kitui county CEP is specific by giving examples of potential development partners for implementation of the projects, the Nakuru and Narok CEPs only mention the potential for partnerships without examples. The Kitui CEP could adopt a table structure such as that adopted by the Narok and Nakuru CEPs to make it easily digestible.

3.8 Implementation, Coordination, Monitoring and Evaluation

This final chapter should contain the plan for implementing the CEP, including how the county shall establish a legislative and regulatory framework for the energy sector. The chapter should also discuss the coordination mechanism at two levels: vertical collaboration with MoE and horizontal coordination at the county level with county departments. In addition, the chapter should also define and describe a monitoring and evaluation mechanism, which should include a schedule showing major activities and those responsible for the recommended energy projects. The main components of this chapter are shown in Table 10.

Table 10: INEP Chapter 8 Requirements

	INEP Requirement	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
1	Legal frameworks for CEP implementation	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Institutional frameworks for CEP implementation	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	Supervisory department highlighted	Yes	No	Yes
4	Vertical coordination with MoE	Yes	No	Yes
5	Horizontal coordination within county	Yes	No	Yes
6	Time schedule with major activities and those responsible for delivery of projects	Yes	No	Yes
	Score	100%	33%	100%

Nakuru CEP: This CEP discusses the institutional setting required for the implementation of the recommendations. It also gives a detailed work plan, budget and methods for monitoring and evaluation. The work plan is divided into quarters of the year and different tasks important for achieving objectives of different programmes allocated the relevant time. A monitoring and evaluation framework with targets is given to allow for day-to-day, quarterly, annual, mid-term, and end-of-term monitoring.

Kitui CEP: The CEP briefly discusses how the solutions outlined can be integrated into the county development planning. It also discusses potential partnerships and the potential for co-financing.

Narok CEP: This section gives the proposed constitution of the CEP implementation committee. It also provides a monitoring and evaluation framework with outcome indicators, mid-term targets, end-targets, evaluation frequency and the department responsible for the review.

Summary: Nakuru and Narok CEPs' monitoring and evaluation plans are elaborate. The Kitui CEP could use more details especially in timelines, monitoring and evaluation criteria and the departments responsible leading on different projects.

4 Conclusion

Table 11 shows a summary of how the various CEPs meet the INEP Chapter requirements. Green means that the CEP chapter achieved a score of above 65%, amber implies that the CEP chapter achieved a score of 50 - 65% while red signifies that the CEP Chapter achieved a score of below 50%. We note that Narok county CEP has met above 65% of INEP requirements for all chapters. The Kitui CEP has done the same in six of the eight chapters, but falls short in the bio-energy chapter and the chapter on implementation, coordination, monitoring and evaluation. The Nakuru CEP has met over 65% of INEP requirements in five out of the eight chapters; the CEP lacks energy efficiency and bio-energy chapters.

Table 11: CEP Review Summary

Chapter	Nakuru	Kitui	Narok
1. Introduction	71%	100%	100%
2. Resource Assessment	80%	80%	100%
3. Energy Access	69%	75%	100%
4. Energy Efficiency	20%	80%	90%
5. Bio-Energy	15%	15%	90%
6. Electricity	50%	86%	86%
7. Programs & Projects	75%	100%	75%
8. Implementation & Monitoring	100%	33%	100%

For the strengths of the CEPs, the Narok CEP is the only CEP that has done a section on waste-to-energy potential and a chapter on bio-energy; the other CEPs could borrow from these sections. The Kitui county CEP has given comprehensive solutions by addressing energy gaps and other enabling factors to ensure that the projects are successful and sustainable. The Nakuru CEP has performed best in budgeting by giving a comprehensive breakdown of the annual budget for different activities; The Nakuru CEP has also laid down a robust monitoring and evaluation framework with targets given to allow for day-to-day, quarterly, annual, mid-term, and end-of-term monitoring.

Other than adding the missing chapter on bio-energy and more details on implementation and monitoring, the Kitui county CEP may be improved by adopting the structure suggested by the INEP framework to make it easily digestible and comparable to the other CEPs. The Nakuru CEP should add the energy efficiency and bio-energy chapters and add modelling on electricity supply in order to meet INEP requirements. The Narok CEP can be improved by addition of a comprehensive explanation of how the modelling scenarios for electricity demand were arrived at; the Narok CEP can also be improved by adding examples of development partners who could help in the implementation of various projects.

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